

Low-cost Radio Frequency Occupancy Measurement System

Lee McQuire¹

¹ Department of Electrical Engineering, Cape Peninsula University of Technology (CPUT), Bellville, South Africa

*mcquir4L@gmail.com

Abstract: In this paper, we will determine the feasibility of installing the RF monitoring station on a moving vehicle. The RF monitoring station will comprise of a Software Defined Radio (SDR), a computer, and GPS that is to be installed on public transport. In utilizing public transport, the radio monitoring system can opportunistically collect measurements while moving through a specific area. These occupancy measurements will provide valuable data about radio spectrum use over a larger area compared to a single location-based station. The RF monitoring system will be simulated in MATLAB to model the systems to be installed on public transport. The emphasis on these simulation models is to optimize the sample rate of occupancy measurements taking into account the distance and travelling speed of public transport. The optimized sample rate will reduce the need for extra processing and storage overhead while keeping to a set prediction accuracy over an area of interest. A hardware prototype will be designed to demonstrate the feasibility of the system and model. The measurement will be plotted on a scatter plot map. The recorded measurement serves as a tool for analysing spectrum occupancy over the geographic area in which public transport frequently travels.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in demand for electromagnetic spectrum resources. As the RF spectrum is a finite resource, there is a constant need to optimise the use of the remaining RF spectrum[1]. One of the ways of optimising the RF spectrum use is to make use of radio monitoring stations[2]. Radio monitoring stations do frequency band occupancy measurements[3]. Commercial RF monitoring systems [4] has a major disadvantage in that they are relatively expensive and complex. Secondly, a great majority of the radio monitoring systems are designed to be installed in a single location only.

The main purpose of this research is to develop a cost-effective RF occupancy measurement system that is based on Software-Defined Radio (SDR) namely RTL-SDR dongle [5][6]. The RTL-SDR can monitor from 25 MHz to 1.7 GHz and is relatively sensitive compared to more expensive monitoring devices[7]. This system is to be installed on public transport to opportunistically collect monitoring information as the transport is moving through an area[8][9]. This approach adds a proportional amount of useful measurement over a very large area. This system needs to be able to record signal strength measurements for a prolonged period with an optimised sample spread over the geographical area without recording too frequently when public transport stops or are moving relatively fast.

2. Mobile deployed Radio Occupancy Measurement

2.1. Spectrum Occupancy

Spectrum occupancy is defined as a portion of the measurement time when the detection power in the band exceeds the decision threshold [10]. Spectrum occupancy measurement is divided into five dimensions that need to be monitored namely; frequency, location, power, direction and

time[11]. On each sample of the occupancy measurements, this information needs to be recorded. When relatively wide

frequency bands are scanned for channel occupancy for a long period of time, a large amount of storage is needed, thus selective filtering and optimising the sampling is necessary.

2.2. Sample Optimisation Simulation Model

To optimise the sampling rate and set the occupancy measurements to a predetermined accuracy, a simulation model is built making use of MATLAB-Simulink [12][13]. The end goal of the simulation is to reduce the number of samples needed by taking into account the speed and distance at which the vehicle is travelling based on the information generated by the GPS.[14][10]. By using these parameters, the number of samples that are stored can be reduced without affecting the overall spectrum plots[15]. The recorded measurement samples can be plotted on a scatter plot by signal strength[16][17].

Fig. 2. Block Diagram of Mobile Deployed Radio Frequency Occupancy Measurement System

2.3. RF Occupancy Prototype Architecture

A prototype of the system is to be built to test the created simulation model. The proper antenna, bandpass filter, GPS and RTL-SDR is selected for this system. The Omni-directional antenna and GPS module are installed on public transport. The directional antenna is connected to a bandpass filter, which is connected to the RTL-SDR. The GPS module and RTL-SDR are connected to the computer for processing and storage (see fig.2). Another contribution to this paper is working on a model to cancel out the internal RF noise of the monitoring system and vehicle. By cancelling out internal RF noise, it will help decrease the possibility of getting false findings[18]. On installation, the vehicle is switched on and a full spectrum sweep is taken using MATLAB software and while RTL-SDR is connected to a 50ohm coupler[19]. The output of this spectrum sweep is saved and used to fine-tune the recorded occupancy results (see Figure 3)[13].

Fig. 3. Spectrum sweep result of the internal noise (orange) of the vehicle plus system and external rf reading (blue) for the FM band spanning from 88 to 108 MHz

3. Conclusion

Spectrum resources is a finite resource and RF occupancy monitoring is one of the tools to optimize RF spectrum. The proposed RF monitoring system will assist with this in a cost-effective way. The proposed RF occupancy monitoring system will be simulated by making use of MATLAB. The simulation model will assist in optimizing the sample rate of occupancy measurements, considering the distance and the traveling speed of public transport. The optimized sample rate aids to reduce storage overhead while keeping to a preset accuracy. The hardware prototype is designed to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed sample model for measurements. By making use of the commercially available RTL-SDR and GPS, the radio frequency occupancy measurement system could be cost-effectively prototyped. The opportunistic collection of measurements and cost-effective design is a major benefit compared to traditional occupancy monitoring systems. The measurements of this system can be used to construct various maps to better determine spectrum use, detect unused channels, estimate its channel quality, find illegal use of the radio spectrum and validate the locations of

primary and secondary devices over a greater area compared to a single location-based radio monitoring station.

4. Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge funding by Cape Peninsula University of Technology (CPUT) and support of staff.

5. References

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Wednesday 25th November 2020

Presented as a track under AIUE Congress 2020

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